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INVESTIGATION OF DAMAGE ACCUMULATION IN GLASS/CARBON FIBER HYBRID COMPOSITES THROUGH ACOUSTIC EMISSION METHOD

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Introduction

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers(CFRP)

- High strength
- Low Density
- Expensive
- Low Fracture Toughness

Glass/Carbon Hybrid Fiber Reinforced Polymers

- Closer Strength to CFRP
- Hybrid Effect [1].
- Low relative cost
- Higher Fracture Toughness

$$\% \text{Hybrid Effect} = 100 \times (\epsilon_{f-HYB} - \epsilon_{f-LE}) / \epsilon_{f-LE}$$

- Safety Factor
- Cost
- Design Flexibility

Failure Mechanisms

- Progressive Failure
- Damage monitoring
- How to monitor failure?

❖ Burst of energy due to damage development causes acoustic waves

❖ Is there any relationship between damage types and AE hits?

Kmeans Clustering Based on Weighted peak frequency and Partial Powers has been reported to be very successful [2,3].

Feature	Definition
Peak Frequency (kHz)	Maximum of frequency spectrum (f_{peak})
Weighted Peak Frequency (kHz)	$f_{WPF} = \sqrt{f_{peak} \cdot f_{centroid}}$
Partial Power 1 (%)	0-200kHz
Partial Power 2 (%)	200-400kHz
Partial Power 3 (%)	400-600kHz
Partial Power 4 (%)	600-800kHz

Experimental

Step 1: Laminate Manufacturing

- 1) Prepare matrix mixture
- 2) Infuse resin into stacked UD dry fibers through VARTM
- 3) Cure at 80°C for 48 hours

Lay up	[C/C/C] _s	[C/G/C] _s	[C/G/G] _s	[G/C/G] _s	[G/G/C] _s
Designation	AC	13C	1C	2C	3C

Step 2: Mechanical tests and AE monitoring [2]

- 1) Cut tensile and bending samples in [0°]
- 2) Prepare test specimens
- 3) Attach AE sensors to the surface and set up AE apparatus.
- 4) Carry out the tensile and flexural tests according to ASTM D3039 and ASTM D790.

Results

❖ 4 clusters are observed for tensile samples while one of these clusters is missing for flexural loading specimens

Weighted Peak Frequency range (kHz)	Damage Type	Tensile tests	Flexural tests
50-160 kHz	Matrix Cracking	✓	✓
150-300 kHz	Interface Failure	✓	✓
300-400kHz	Fiber Pull out	✓	✗
400-600 kHz	Fiber Breakage	✓	✓

❖ Result of clustering for 1C Tensile sample

❖ Hybrid Effect and mechanical properties results for hybrid and non-hybrid laminates:

❖ Spectrograms of sample signals from each cluster

Conclusions

- ✓ To get the highest hybrid effect in flexural samples it is better to put carbon layers in middle plies.
- ✓ Lower ratio of carbon to glass plies results in a reduction of tensile elastic modulus, However it does not necessarily increase hybrid effect value as in the case of 13C laminate.
- ✓ The cluster related to fiber pull-out is not present for flexural tests which is due to the rareness of this damage under bending load conditions.
- ✓ It is seen that for a damage type in which a single composite constituent fails, the energy of the wave is concentrated in a narrow frequency region for a short period of time. On the other hand, for failure types that consist of two material types involved, the structure of spectrogram shows energy spread through a wider frequency spectrum and for a longer time period.

References

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